

Integrating the synchronization stacks of a heterogeneous time-sensitive networking system with wired and wireless domains

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ABSTRACT

This contribution recounts the experience and main integration challenges of the different precision time protocol (PTP)-based synchronization stacks present in the demonstrator of the heterogeneous time-sensitive networking (TSN) architecture of the TIMING project with wired and wireless segments. This demonstrator represents a significant initiative aimed at showcasing the feasibility of deploying complex, real-time industrial control and robotics systems over large areas by leveraging the deterministic and resilient transport capabilities of TSN in combination with advanced orchestration, optimization methodologies, and commercial telecommunication networks. The end-to-end distribution of a unified time reference is essential to achieve a successful integration. To that end, it is imperative to verify the interoperability between the PTP stacks of the different segments of the network. Hence, we focus on the description of the main scenarios, challenges, and hurdles that had to be overcome to allow the seamless propagation of PTP between the wireless-TSN devices and the Ethernet-based TSN switches present in the demonstrator. This will include an analysis of the applicable profiles and configuration options, suitable for the demonstrator, their effects on performance, as well as lessons learned during the process and considerations for future large-scale deployments of TSN systems.

Keywords: TSN, wireless-TSN, PTP, IEEE1588, synchronization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Real-time communications play a pivotal role in driving the advancements of Industry 4.0, revolutionizing manufacturing processes through seamless connectivity and data exchange. At the heart of this transformation lies TSN, a critical technology which enables the coexistence of time-critical and best-effort traffic while keeping the strict behaviour required by time-critical applications. Clock synchronization is considered as the TSN core functionality since TSN is built upon the condition of a common time shared among the network [1]. In order to perform time synchronization in industrial networks, IEEE 1588 standard, commonly known as PTP, is the de facto standard because of its simplicity and precision in the tens of nanoseconds range using appropriate implementations. However, achieving this clock synchronization presents challenges, particularly in deployments like the one in the TIMING project [2], which encompasses both wireless and wired TSN segments and incorporates network devices that interchangeably utilize PTPd or PTP4L as the PTP stack. Therefore, this paper aims to evaluate the performance of the clock synchronization achieved in the heterogeneous demonstration setup of the TIMING project.

The rest of the article is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a brief introduction to the TIMING project and outlines the specifics of its setup. Section 3 describes the setups used and details the tests conducted. Section 4 analyses the results obtained. Finally, Section 5 draws some conclusions and highlights other important topics that need to be considered.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE TIMING PROJECT: HETEROGENEOUS TSN AND WIRELESS NETWORKS FOR INDUSTRIAL CONTROL

The TIMING project aims to design, implement, and validate a solution to enable end-to-end reliable TSN services supported by operators' infrastructures that are currently carrying traffic on a best effort basis. A high-level description of the project components is depicted in Figure 1. The scenario considered is composed of two factory premises interconnected through a transport network. The factory floors will be equipped with TSN-enabled Wi-Fi and Ethernet network devices, and interconnected by means of a transport network able to cope with the TSN requirements imposed by the end-to-end services to be conveyed over the infrastructure. Hence, the scenario is composed of two types of control domains (i.e., the factory floor and the transport network) each one implementing its own SDN-based control, and all of them connected to the orchestration layer residing on top.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup is targeted at verifying the interoperability between the different PTP synchronization stacks present in the diverse devices in the above presented heterogeneous architecture, ranging from fully wireless-based solutions for efficient synchronization and data transport to the mobile elements, e.g., automated

Figure 1: The TIMING project setup.

guided vehicles (AGVs), of the final demonstration setup, and all the way to Ethernet-based TSN switches and generic telecommunication carrier equipment for deterministic communication. Hence, thorough interoperability testing can be a daunting task, and thus this contribution focuses on the results of the synchronization interoperability tests, which are reported in this section, and which are at the foundation of deterministic networking to ensure the consistent forwarding and shaping of traffic with respect to a common time reference.

Specifically, our study considers the interoperability between the TSN-capable nodes of Safran, and the wireless TSN system of IKERLAN. These two families of devices will have to interact directly with each other in the final demonstration setup of the project, and hence verifying the proper interworking of their synchronization is a must. To that end, we have devised two main setups to study different synchronization interoperability aspects. These can be examined in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The former represents a simplified deployment of the final TIMING architecture and will be used for long-term tests to account for stability and performance of the integration, whereas the latter is a minimalistic test setup that is intended to directly verify the back-to-back interoperability and operation between the timing stacks of Safran and IKERLAN with short-term tests.

Figure 2. Simplified setup for long-term stability and interoperability verification between PTP4L and PTPd.

Figure 3. Minimalistic setup for short-term interoperability tests of PTP4L.

The equipment deployed for the setups in the preceding figures includes devices from both vendors. Thus, the wireless segment of the network is supplied by IKERLAN, and includes a wireless access point (AP), and a remote end station (STA) [3]. Safran is then tasked with handling the Ethernet-based segment of the demonstrator, and hence it is responsible for providing its TSN-Z16 switching nodes [4] for data handling and timing distribution. Safran also provides the overall time reference of the system through a SecureSync module [5], which supplies a GNSS-grade time reference to the grand master TSN switch of the network. The results are measured using a Keysight 53230A frequency counter to evaluate the synchronization offset between the master and slave devices of the network by directly comparing their pulse-per-second (PPS) time difference. The measurements and tests performed for each setup are described in the following sections.

3.1 Interoperability goals and test description.

Our tests consist of a series of iterations that study the effect of applying different synchronization stacks and varying settings between the Safran and IKERLAN nodes with the goal of verifying their interworking and determining a candidate set of settings suitable for use in the final deployment of the project. Safran's appliances can implement both the PTPd [6] and PTP4L [7] timing stacks, although they are transitioning to a PTP4L-only design; whereas IKERLAN's design is based on PTP4L. Thus, these tests will look at the interoperation of these two PTP stacks to find a stable PTPd-PTP4L configuration that could support the use of the legacy PTPd implementation of Safran in the final scenario of the project should it be required. This will be studied with the setup of Figure 2. In addition, we will also validate that Safran's upcoming PTP4L update can operate jointly with IKERLAN's implementation to find a candidate PTP4L-only configuration for the final scenario of TIMING with

the setup of Figure 3. The settings for this batch of tests, and their corresponding description, can be found in Table 1, for the long-term stability and PTPd-PTP4L verification, and in Table 2 for the back-to-back PTP4L tests.

3.1.1 Long-term stability and PTPd-PTP4L interoperability

This test has a twofold goal. On the one hand, it attempts to validate the interoperability between the PTPd and PTP4L stacks. On the other, once interoperability can be verified, it characterizes the attainable stability of the synchronization through a long-term 10-hour test. The applicable settings for this test are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of the long-term PTPd-PTP4L interoperability test.

Test ID	Setup	PTP Stack	Profile	Delay Mechanism	Sync/Delay req. freq.	Transport	Correction
<i>T0</i>	<i>Figure 2</i>	<i>PTPd/PTP4L</i>	-	<i>E2E, two-step</i>	<i>1 packet/s</i>	<i>UDP, Unicast</i>	<i>No</i>

3.1.2 Back-to-back interoperability testing of the PTP4L implementations of IKERLAN and Safran

This verifies that the latest upgrades to Safran’s nodes to provide compatibility with PTP4L are functional and capable of interoperating with IKERLAN’s devices realistically. This characterization is of special interest, as the final project scenario will likely be based on PTP4L synchronization entirely, and thus the operation of the implementations of PTP4L from both vendors should provide stable synchronization with comparable accuracy to the fallback, legacy configuration characterized in Section 3.1.1. This is studied through a batch of tests summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Overview of the back-to-back PTP4L interoperability tests between Safran and IKERLAN.

Test ID	Setup	PTP Stack	Profile	Delay Mechanism	Sync/Delay req. freq.	Transport	Correction
<i>T1</i>	<i>Figure 3</i>	<i>PTP4L</i>	<i>Custom</i>	<i>P2P, two-step</i>	<i>1 packet/s</i>	<i>L2, Multicast</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>T2</i>	<i>Figure 3</i>	<i>PTP4L</i>	<i>Custom</i>	<i>P2P, two-step</i>	<i>16 packet/s</i>	<i>L2, Multicast</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>T3</i>	<i>Figure 3</i>	<i>PTP4L</i>	<i>Default</i>	<i>P2P, two-step</i>	<i>1 packet/s</i>	<i>L2, Multicast</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>T4</i>	<i>Figure 3</i>	<i>PTP4L</i>	<i>Default</i>	<i>P2P, two-step</i>	<i>1 packet/s</i>	<i>L2, Multicast</i>	<i>-120 ns</i>
<i>T5</i>	<i>Figure 3</i>	<i>PTP4L</i>	<i>Custom</i>	<i>E2E, two-step</i>	<i>1 packet/s</i>	<i>UDP, Unicast</i>	<i>-120 ns</i>

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents and discusses the experimental results of the tests for evaluating the interoperability and performance of the different PTP stacks introduced in the previous section.

4.1 Results of the long-term PTPd-PTP4L interoperability test

This test has verified that both PTP stacks are interoperable and capable of attaining a stable synchronization state over the long term. This has been characterized with the Allan deviation of the PPS time difference measured with the counter and is depicted in Figure 4, which shows that the synchronization remains stable over a 10-hour period with an average accuracy on the order of tens of nanoseconds for 1-second averaging windows ($Tau=0$). This indicates that using the legacy PTPd implementation of Safran could be a viable option providing a robust, end-to-end timing reference to the final setup of the project; all the way from the Ethernet-based segment of the demonstrator through to its wireless segment.

4.2 Results of the back-to-back PTP4L interoperability tests

These tests represent the follow-up to the initial PTPd interoperability testing by verifying that Safran’s shift to PTP4L is capable of interworking with IKERLAN’s nodes and provide comparable results to our initial tests with PTPd. We have verified this iteratively by testing different configurations of the default and custom PTP profiles, as indicated in Table 2. The results are presented graphically in the histogram plot of Figure 5, with more detailed information summarized in Table 3.

These results show that the initial integration of the PTP4L stacks of IKERLAN and Safran has been successful, with mostly stable synchronization distribution between the master and slave devices, and only an occasional loss of synchronization in test T3. Moreover, the peak-to-peak PPS offset value remains stable in all cases, at the ~100 ns range, except for test T3, which has a somewhat degraded performance of ~600 ns on account of one single instance of a sudden loss of synchronization. Nonetheless, these values are in keeping with the expected performance of a hardware-based PTP4L implementation. It should be noted that, even though synchronization remains stable throughout the tests, we could observe a shift in the mean value of the PPS offset towards ~400 ns in the initial iterations of the tests (T1, T2, T3). The last two remaining iterations (T4 and T5) attempt to compensate for these offset values by supplying a user-defined correction of 120 ns, which had the effect of lowering the average offset to the range ~100 ns.

Figure 4. Allan deviation plot of the long-term PTPd-PTP4L interoperability test.

Figure 5. PPS synchronization offset comparison for different settings in the PTP4L interoperability tests.

Consequently, the results of this early integration of the PTP4L stacks of IKERLAN and Safran are promising and show that the final scenario of the project could effectively converge to a design based entirely on PTP4L. Some aspects, such as the initial ~400 ns offset of the first iterations or the sudden loss of synchronization of test T3, should still be investigated further to determine possible issues related to the calibration of our devices that should be addressed.

Table 3. Results of the back-to-back PTP4L interoperability tests with comments.

Test ID	Mean PPS Offset (ns)	Peak-to-peak PPS Offset (ns)	Test Results and observations
T1	410.391	80.391	- Works & Stable - Constant master-slave offset of ~400 ns
T2	406.838	81.606	
T3	421.508	670.840	- Works & Stable but occasional synchronization loss - Constant master-slave offset of ~400 ns but with worst-case offset difference peaking at 671 ns before regaining lock
T4	78.804	78.013	- Works & Stable. - Added user-defined correction offset compensation of -120 ns lowers the constant ~400 ns offset to ~70ns
T5	69.805	96.016	

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this article we deal with the evaluation of the interoperability and performance of several PTP stack implementations such as PTPd and PTP4L, as well as various configurations/profiles of these stacks over an experimental setup that encompasses both wired and wireless TSN segments. The results obtained indicate that by properly adjusting the different parameters of the PTP stacks, it is possible to achieve interoperability between them and attain a common clock reference with precision in the range of tens of nanoseconds, both in wired and wireless network elements. This synchronization precision will enable the future deployment of TSN services over the TIMING project architecture.

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